

Vibro-Punching of KEVLAR Aramid and Carbon Fiber Reinforced Composites

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ABSTRACT

Kevlar-49 aramid or carbon fiber reinforced composite materials are difficult to be cut and machined without the defects such as delamination, crack, bulging and fuzzing. Moreover the cutting tool life is extraordinarily short. For solving these problems we have tried to apply a mirror finish punching technique, "Vibro-Punching", chiefly to the piercing of riveting or fastening hole in these composites used in the aircraft. The hole surface was confirmed experimentally to be finished to the glossy face with the perfect linear section and R_{max} 5 - 9 μ m, in 0.4 - 0.8 seconds of punch-vibrating time without almost any troubles. In addition, the dimensional accuracy of the pierced hole may be as high as the one in the fine blanking of metal sheets. These results tell that the Vibro-Punching may be the technique being capable of replacing the present drilling and machining.

1. INTRODUCTION

The composites reinforced with Kevlar-49 aramid and carbon fibers have the excellent balanced properties of the light weight, high tensile strength and high modulus. Therefore the composites and their hybrids are broadly applied to structural components of the aircraft, the aerospace and the other general industrial products. The composite sheets like aircraft components require the trimming, machining or drilling in the subsequent process after sheet forming, while most of the composites have the poor characteristics of machinability. Above all, the Kevlar aramid composite is one of the most difficult materials for machining. There often remain the fuzzing, bulging and delaminations at the edge machined by the conventional ways. Especially in the CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic), not only do the chipping and the delaminations occur at the machined edge, but also the cutting tool life is extraordinarily short. Accordingly the special techniques such as water jet and laser beam have been searched in the past for cutting these composite materials(1).

We have already developed a new vibration press punching process "Vibro-Punching", which provides mirror finish holes in the Glass/Epoxy laminates utilized for printed wiring boards(2). In this research work, we newly challenge the Kevlar-49/Epoxy and Carbon/Epoxy composite sheets to be punched by Vibro-Punching. Through the experimental investigations of making a riveting or fastening hole in these composites, we further discuss the utilization of this process in the blanking or shearing of them.

2. VIBRO-PUNCHING

The basic action of the Vibro-Punching process is shown schematically in Fig.1. Clamped between two sets of upper and lower dies as [1], a composite sheet is pierced by a couple of vibrating punches. Both top and bottom punches move in unison and finish vibrating after the required amount of frequencies, when the neutral vibrating point shifts down from the initial vibrating position so that the slug may be pierced out of the sheet as shown in [4]. During these vibrations, the temperature of the matrix resin in the shearing zone rises and it becomes more viscous. After the stop of the punch vibration, the outer surface of the piercing punch is copied onto the inner surface of the punched hole and a mirror finished surface of the hole is obtained.

3. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Figure 2 illustrates the experimental apparatus for Vibro-Punching, which is similar to a low cycle fatigue testing machine. A sample sheet to be pierced is put into the gap between two sets of tools and clamped by them. As vibrating conditions are set to the control unit and the actuator begins to operate, both punches can vibrate according to the displacement of the frame which is moved by the actuator. Table 1 describes the experimental conditions and Table 2 shows the characteristics of Kevlar composites and CFRP to be pierced in the experiment. We have adopted a simple wave-mode of punch vibration in Fig.3 in terms of the efficiency in finishing holes, the tool wear and its practicability. Here we have adjusted the initial clamping pressure of tools by changing the torque of each bolt for pressing them.

Fig.1 Schematic procedures of Vibro-Punching

Fig.2 Experimental apparatus for Vibro-Punching

Table 1 Experimental conditions

●Wave: Sine wave
Amplitude(per one side)0.33mm
Frequency 50Hz
●Punch diameter: ϕ 4mm
●Clearance between punch and die: 0.01mm(per one side)
●Lubrication between punch and die: Unlubricated
●Initial punch pressure: 156MPa
●Initial die pueasure: 64MPa

Fig. 3 Punch vibration wave-mode used in the experiment of Vibro-Punching

Table 2 Characteristics of the Kevlar composites and CFRP used in the experiment

	Matrix resin	Cloth Style	Ply	Fabric vol. %	Tensile strength(MPa)	Shear strength(MPa)	Sheet thickness(mm)
Kevlar-49 composites	Epoxy	Satin (K285)	8	40	380	40	2.4
CFRP	Epoxy	Plain	10	60	480	48	1.9

4. VIBRO-PUNCHING OF COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH KEVLAR-49 ARAMID

4.1 Appearances of the pierced holes in the Kevlar composites

Figure 4 shows the appearances of pierced holes by drilling, punching and Vibro-Punching. Around the drilled hole, the fuzzing that must be removed afterward occurs as shown in Fig.4-i). The hole of Fig.4-ii) was provided by the conventional punching and the hole of Fig.4-iii) was by the punching with 64MPa blank-holding pressure. Kevlar yarn is so tough and not brittle that many fibers like whiskers remain pulled-out mainly around the hole ii),iii) on the lower side pierced by punching. We can also observe a wide whitened swelling A and delaminations in the hole ii). Differing from them, Vibro-Punching can restrain these defects to a great extent as shown in Fig.4-v) and vi). A little fuzzing remains around the hole iv) under the condition of $T_1=0.0$ sec., while almost no fuzz appears under $T_1=0.6$

Fig.4 Appearances of the pierced holes in the composites reinforced with Kevlar

i) Pressure Punching in Fig.4-iii) ii) Vibro-Punching in Fig.4-iv) iii) Vibro-Punching in Fig.4-v) iv) Vibro-Punching in Fig.4-vi)

Fig.5 Magnified hole-edges in the composites reinforced with Kevlar

sec., because the fuzzy fibers have been gradually cut or torn off during the reciprocative shearing movement. The partial hole edges of iii)-vi) in Fig.4 are magnified in Fig.5, which indicates that Vibro-punching can give us almost perfect edge without fuzzing.

4.2 Properties of holes pierced in the composites reinforced with Kevlar

Figure 6 shows the surface roughness curves and cross sectional shapes of the holes in Fig.4. We easily notice the bulging A,B in the drilling i), and that the swelling C in the conventional punching ii) in Fig.6. The hole surfaces of i)-iii) in Fig.6 are considerably rough; namely, the surface roughness of the drilling i) is R_{max} 25 μ m and those of the usual punching ii), iii) are R_{max} 40-50 μ m. As compared with them, Vibro-Punching holes of iv),v) in Fig.6 are remarkably flat and smooth such that the hole surface roughness of R_{max} 8 μ m under the condition of $T_1=0.6$ sec. is about one-third of the drilled one. Fig.7 is the scanning electron micrograph of the each hole surface in Fig.6. The drilled face in Fig.7-i) has an uneven cut surface, and the punched face ii) is covered with pulled-out fibers stretching into the punching direction. As shown in Fig.7-iii),

Fig.6 Surface roughness curves and cross sectional shapes of the holes in Fig.4 pierced by the several ways in the composites reinforced with Kevlar

i) Drilling in Fig.4 -i) ii) Pressure punching -iii) iii) Vibro-Punching -v)

Fig.7 Scanning electron micrographs of the hole surfaces in Fig.4

Vibro-Punching can produce a uniform and flat surface, where some bent Kevlar fibers appear on the finished face like iii)-A. Fig.8 is the cross section of the Vibro-Punched face iii) in Fig.7. Because the Kevlar fibers are very flexible and tough, the yarns which parallel the sheet surfaces can easily turn their direction along the hole surface at 0.1-0.2 mm away from the hole. In the Vibro-Punching process of the Kevlar composites the hole surface is finished in the form that the space between their fibers, including the short-cut ones, is buried with the resin softened by temperature rise.

4.3 Punch load variation in the Vibro-Punching process of Kevlar composites

The punch load variation accompanied by the tool vibration is shown in Fig.9. After sudden rise to a peak load A at the first punch vibration, the punch load gradually drops down during the stage T_1 , in which the Kevlar fibers are cut by degrees under the repeated severe tensile or compressive deformations and the heat generation in the shearing zone. When the vibrating punches begin to descend, a high peak B appears and afterward the punching load decreases rapidly. This is because the rest of many unbroken fibers are cut by the stretch in the punch descent stage. The load of the peak B is 70 percent of the conventional punching load, which is estimated to play an important role in restraining the delaminations and the other break-out damages.

Fig.8 Cross section of the Vibro-Punched hole(Fig.4-v)) in the Kevlar composites

Fig.9 Punch load variation curve in the Vibro-Punching process of Kevlar composites

5. VIBRO-PUNCHING OF COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH CARBON FIBERS

5.1 Properties of the holes pierced in the CFRP

Figure 10 is the appearances of a hole in the CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic) pierced by the Vibro-Punching process. Fig.11 shows the hole surface roughness and its sectional shape pierced by each process in the following: i) drilling at 12000 rpm on the backing board, ii) punching with 64 MPa blank-holding pressure and iii) Vibro-Punching under $T_1 = T_2 = 0.2$ sec.. The CFRP as well as the GFRP is characterized by the high tensile strength and the high modulus, while fibers in the composites are considerably brittle. Therefore especially in the conventional punching, all the hole surface becomes very uneven broken faces as shown in Fig.11-ii), out of which many carbon fibers protrude. In the drilling of Fig.11 -i), the wear of the cutting tool readily results in bulging or chipping at a hole edge as compared with them, the Vibro-Punching process can easily and constantly form a flat and glossy finish surface of R_{max} 5-8 μ m within only 0.4 sec., as shown in Fig.10 and Fig.11.

5.2 Observation of the finished surface of CFRP pierced by Vibro-Punching

Figure 12 and Figure 13 show the scanning electron micrographs of the finished surface by Vibro-Punching and its cross section respectively. The finished surface in the CFRP is uniformly covered with about 0.1mm thickness compound layer of the broken fiber pieces and resin, under which the rough cross section of the perfectly fractured fabric lies as observed in Fig.13. The compound layer is formed during repeated shearing and crushing process in the cracking and deforming zone. While vibrating punches are descending in the last stage of punching, the smooth surface of the punch side is copied onto the heat-softened resin in the compound layer around the hole. After all, the hole surface is finished nearly to the roughness of the tool surface.

Fig.10 Appearances of the hole pierced by the Vibro-Punching in the CFRP

Fig.11 Surface roughness curves and cross sectional shapes of the holes pierced by the several ways in the CFRP

Fig.12 Scanning electron micrograph of the hole surface finished by Vibro-Punching process in the CFRP

Fig.13 Cross section of the Vibro-Punched hole in the CFRP (SEM)

5.3 Punch load variation in the Vibro-Punching process of the CFRP

Figure 14 is the punch load variation curve in the Vibro-Punching of the CFRP. As soon as the punches start to vibrate, the punching load jumps to the same peak level obtained in the conventional punching. After this peak C, the punch load falls so rapidly that the value of the load D after 10 vibrations almost one-seventh of the maximum punching load C. Here in the descent of the neutral vibrating position, we couldn't find a distinguished increase of the punching load, which was clearly observed in the Kevlar composites. These facts indicate that the carbon fibers in the shearing zone are completely fractured during the first or the second punch cycle of vibration. After the cracks have penetrated through the sheet, these initial fractured faces are rubbed and smoothed in the subsequent reciprocative punching movement. Then, the fibers are broken to short pieces and the resin is softened by the generated heat between both fractured faces.

6. DIMENSIONAL ACCURACY OF THE PIERCED HOLES BY VIBRO-PUNCHING

For investigating the dimensional accuracy of the Vibro-Punching holes, we have measured the hole diameters on both sides of the sheet. Fig.15 shows the results in the measurement of 10 samples for each composites under the piercing conditions of Fig.4-v) and Fig.11-iii). Since the hole surface contacts with the punch outer surface at the end of processing, the average of the hole diameters is nearly equal to the punch diameter though it becomes a little smaller due to the elastic contraction after stripping from punch. In the Kevlar composites, the hole on the lower side is smaller than the one on the upper side by 0.03 to 0.04mm in diameter. On the contrary in the CFRP, the hole on the lower side is larger than the upper one approximately by the value corresponding to the tool clearance. This difference probably comes from the characteristics of these two composites: namely, modulus, toughness and ductility. The difference between the maximum and the minimum measured values of the hole diameters is 100 to 110 μm in the Kevlar composites, and 30 to 40 μm in the CFRP. The comparatively extensive distributions in the Kevlar composites can be attributed to a reading error owing to a little fuzzing originated in the hole edge. The dimensional stability shown in the narrow distribution range proves Vibro-Punching to be the most available technique for precision hole piercing.

Fig. 14 Punch load variation curve in the Vibro-Punching process of the CFRP

Fig. 15 Dimensional accuracy of the Vibro-Punched hole

7. CONCLUSIONS

We have tried to apply the Vibro-Punching to the piercing of the composites reinforced with Kevlar-49 aramid and the CFRP. The conclusions obtained in the experimental investigation are summarized in the following ;

- (1) In the composites reinforced with Kevlar, Vibro-Punching can provide a riveting or fastening hole without fuzzing, bulging and delaminations, and the hole surface is finished in 0.8 sec. to the R_{max} 6-9 μ m flat and uniform face which is superior to the drilled one.
- (2) In the CFRP, Vibro-Punching can make a smooth hole with the glossy face (R_{max} 5-8 μ m) and the almost perfect straight section, only in 0.4 sec. without chipping and bulging.
- (3) The dimensional accuracy of the Vibro-Punched holes in these composites may be as high as the one in the fine blanking of metal sheets.

These results mean that the Vibro-Punching can be a precision punching technique being capable of replacing the drilling and machining. Within the scope of this paper, one punch cycle time was 0.4 to 0.8 sec., but according to the experimental results in the GFRP, the cycle time can be probably reduced to 0.2-0.4 sec. by a higher amplitude, frequency or greater sheet clamping force. The problems solved in the future are the establishment of the optimum punching conditions, the durability of tools, the development of the practical Vibro-Punching machine. Now a prototype commercial Vibro-Punching press has already been designed and will be produced for punching these composites for the aircraft.

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